

Notas breves

Not Rissoidae but heterobranchs: the Azorean “*Setia*” *alexandrae* and “*Setia*” *ermelindoi* reassigned to the genus *Rissoella* Gray, 1847 (Gastropoda, Rissoellidae)

No son Rissoidae sino heterobranquios: “*Setia*” *alexandrae* y “*Setia*” *ermelindoi* de las Azores reasignadas al género *Rissoella* Gray, 1847 (Gastropoda, Rissoellidae)

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In a recent paper, CORDEIRO & ÁVILA (2015) described four new species of Azorean Rissoidae, three of which were placed in the genus *Setia* H. & A. Adams. As currently understood, this genus comprises small species, with rather featureless shells lacking both axial and spiral sculpture, and is most likely to be a polyphyletic assemblage. Two Macaronesian species have been recently transferred to *Crisilla* (OLIVER, ROLÁN & TEMPLADO, 2019).

The Rissoid animal is quite characteristic (see GOFAS, 1990 for several examples of Azorean species). The head bears a well developed snout and elongate, smooth and parallel-sided cephalic tentacles placed laterally to the snout. The eyes are situated on the outer side of the tentacles, in a little bulge near their base. The foot is clearly differentiated in propodium and metapodium, separated by a median constriction, the anterior part truncated and cleft by the opening of the anterior pedal gland. The operculum

is paucispiral and, posterior to it, the foot usually bears one or several metapodial tentacles which provide a useful taxonomic character at the genus level. The edge of the mantle may bear small pallial tentacles, one (right) at the point where the outer lip meets the parietal edge of the aperture, and another one opposite to it at the level of the columella.

The external anatomy of *Rissoella*, a heterobranch genus with shells superficially resembling rissoids, is quite different. FRETTER (1948) had already described *Rissoella diaphana* (Alder, 1848), type species of the genus by subsequent designation of Petit (2012) under ICZN Art. 70.3.2, and *Rissoella opalina*, also present in the same environment of tidal pools in SW England. The animal of *Rissoella diaphana* (Figures 1-2) has a proportionally large head, with a flat and bilobed snout; the cephalic tentacles are also flat, longer than the snout and tapering to a blunt end. Contrary to rissoids

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Figures 1-2. *Rissoella diaphana* (Alder, 1848), living animal from Pointe Sainte Barbe, Saint Jean de Luz, SW Atlantic coast of France, intertidal zone (shell 2.0 mm). 3-4. *Rissoella opalina* (Jeffreys, 1848), living specimen from Sagres, southern Portugal, intertidal zone (shell 1.5 mm). Figures 5-6. *Rissoella alexandrae* (Ávila & Cordeiro, 2015), living animal from Ponta Delgada, Azores, 0-1 m (shell 1.25 mm). 7-8. *Rissoella ermelindoi* (Ávila & Cordeiro, 2015), living animal from Ilheu de Vilafranca, Azores, 0-1 m (shell 0.9 mm).

Figuras 1-2. *Rissoella diaphana* (Alder, 1848), animal vivo de Pointe Sainte Barbe, Saint Jean de Luz, costa Atlántica del suroeste de Francia, zona intermareal (concha de 2,0 mm). 3-4. *Rissoella opalina* (Jeffreys, 1848), animal vivo de Sagres, sur de Portugal, zona intermareal (concha de 1.5 mm). Figuras 5-6. *Rissoella alexandrae* (Ávila & Cordeiro, 2015), animal vivo de Ponta Delgada, Azores, 0-1 m (concha de 1,25 mm). 7-8. *Rissoella ermelindoi* (Ávila & Cordeiro, 2015), animal vivo de Ilheu de Vilafranca, Azores, 0-1 m (concha de 0.9 mm)

where the eyes are always lateral to the tentacles, the eyes of *Rissoella* are embedded within the head, situated along the axis of the tentacles, and do not form a bulge. The foot is truncated anteriorly but not distinctly differentiated in a propodium and metapodium. The very distinctive operculum is not spirally coiled but grows concentrically, and there is no metapodial tentacle. The mantle is clearly seen by transparency on living animals and has extensive dark brown areas, among which the pig-

mented mantle organ, characteristic of heterobranch gastropods, can be seen as yellow granules. There are no pallial tentacles. The animals of several Caribbean species of *Rissoella* were illustrated by ORTEA AND ESPINOSA (2005) and by CABALLER, ORTEA AND REDFERN (2014), those of some North Pacific species by SIADÉN ET AL. (2019), and some patterns show a remarkable homogeneity across many species. *Rissoella opalina* (Figures 3-4) is somewhat different from the type species: the snout has smaller, rounded

lobes, the tentacles are distinctly bifid, the two branches approximately of equal length and the pigmented mantle organ forms a distinct loop visible on the last whorl.

Field notes gathered during the author’s visits to the Azores in 1990-1991 included drawings of living animals, which at the time were identified as *Rissoella* aff. *diaphana* and *Rissoella* aff. *opalina*., and correspond respect lively to *Setia alexandrae* and *Setia ermelindoi*. These drawings are here reproduced (Fig. 5-8) and support the conclusion that these two species must be reassigned. Therefore, the new combinations *Rissoella alexandrae* and *Rissoella ermelindoi* are formally proposed. The former species is strikingly similar to *R. diaphana*, except for its somewhat smaller size. The latter resembles *R. opalina* by the ovoid outline of the shell but seems unrelated to it, the head has simple

triangular tentacles like *R. diaphana* and *R. alexandrae*, not bifid as in *R. opalina*.

The holotype of the third “*Setia*” species, “*Setia*” *netoae*, described by Cordero & Ávila is almost certainly also a *Rissoella* but was not among the species observed alive during the 1990-1991 field trips. It differs from *Rissoella alexandrae* in being slightly larger, with less convex whorls, but its relationships require further work; conversely the paratype 7 (Cordeiro & Ávila 2015, Fig. 3D) from Flores island is definitely a rissoid, probably undescribed, as denoted by the opaque shell and the thick peristome.

Rissoella is a quite species-rich genus, with sixty currently accepted species worldwide (WoRMS editorial board, 2019) of which one-third were described in this century. With the addition of two or three more species in the supposedly well-known European realm shows that the richness in this group is still underrated.

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